

**ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ДИАЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО
ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА С ОБЩИМ НЕДОРАЗВИТИЕМ РЕЧИ В
ПРОЦЕССЕ ЛОГОПЕДИЧЕСКОЙ РАБОТЫ**

**DEVELOPING DIALOGIC SPEECH THROUGH SPEECH THERAPY IN
CHILDREN OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL AGE WITH GENERAL SPEECH
UNDERDEVELOPMENT**

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В статье описаны особенности формирования диалогической речи у старших дошкольников с общим недоразвитием речи в процессе логопедической работы. Указаны научные исследования в области лингвистики, психолингвистики, психологии и педагогике, которые связаны с изучением диалогической речи у дошкольников с общим недоразвитием речи. Описаны этапы логопедической работы по формированию диалогической речи у старших дошкольников с общим недоразвитием речи. Представлен анализ адаптированных программ дошкольного образования для детей с тяжелыми нарушениями речи, с целью выявления методов, форм, системы логопедической работы по формированию диалогической речи у старших дошкольников с общим недоразвитием речи.

The article describes the features of the formation of dialogic speech in older preschoolers with general underdevelopment of speech in the process of speech therapy. Scientific research in the field of linguistics, psycholinguistics, psychology and pedagogy, which are associated with the study of dialogical speech in preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment, is indicated. The stages of speech therapy work on the formation of dialogic speech in older preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment are described. The analysis of adapted preschool education programs for children with severe speech disorders is present-

ed in order to identify methods, forms, and systems of speech therapy work on the formation of dialogic speech in older preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment.

Ключевые слова: диалог, речь, старшие дошкольники, общее недоразвитие речи, логопедическая работа.

Key words: dialogue, speech, children of senior preschool age, general speech underdevelopment, speech therapy.

Dialogical speech habits have a major impact on child's personality and their social adaptation. In this regard, developing dialogical speech in children of senior preschool age is an urgent problem today.

According to the Federal State Educational Standard for preschool education, educational program content should apply to all types of speech activities, so that each child would develop personal, motivational and creative potential [6].

Developing speech in children of senior preschool age involves developing dialogic communication skill. Successful communication depends on many interrelated factors, including: speech of the people around, a family social status, a child's personality, his individual and age peculiarities, etc. All these factors should be the supporting ground from which preschoolers develop their speech. A child interacts with society through speech, which is considered to be a communicative function. It is reflected in child's behavior. Developing a speech function, preschoolers start seeking to master their native language with all its components. And dialogue is becoming a key form of communication.

Developing dialogic communication skills in children with general speech underdevelopment not only successfully targets current social tasks, but also prepares children for a new education level – schooling.

Noteworthy, some dialogic speech components in preschool children with general speech underdevelopment are not adequately developed. As a rule, this is affected by poor motivation and cognitive activity, as well as an inadequately developed skill to construct sentences, and defective pronunciation as such. These children have poor vocabulary, which also affects speech literacy.

As a result, the approaches to work with these children should be somewhat different. Practices that are effective for developing dialogic speech in preschoolers with general speech underdevelopment are to be selected [1].

Various sciences deal with dialogic speech studies, including: linguistics, psycholinguistics, psychology and pedagogy. Representatives of these sciences (L.P. Yakubinsky, M.M. Bakhtin, M.M. Lisina, O.A. Kapitovskaya, M.G. Plokhotnyuk) took an in-depth look at the problem of dialogic speech development. Scientists have comprehensively analyzed the dialogic speech aspects. Some scientists (O.M. Vershina, V.P. Glukhov, O.Ya. Goikhman, etc.) believe that dialogue speech is effective in developing a cognitive function, since we receive information through social speech interaction mainly. Otherwise, cognitive process development slows down. Other specialists (N.S. Zhukova, E.M. Mastyukova, S.A. Mironova, etc.) specify that an insufficiently developed speech function limits the child in social communication.

Some scientists (M.I. Lisina, V.S. Mukhina, A.G. Ruzskaya, E.O. Smirnova, E.A. Trofimova, etc.) tend to believe that the basic ability of a child to communicate in a dialogue form is the foundation for the ability to build a coherent monologue preserving logical connections and a sequence of utterances.

When developing speech, dialogic skills are first mastered, and then monologue skills are developed. However, these speech forms are subsequently corrected and improved simultaneously.

Today, special pedagogy and psychology are interested in dealing with the problem of developing speech interaction skills in preschool children with general speech underdevelopment, and is constantly looking for new tools to develop to productive communication with dialogue participants. Therefore, developing dialogic speech is one of the key tasks. Many factors contribute to speech development, in particular: speech environment, social, individual and personal peculiarities, cognitive activity, etc. These factors are important to be considered when developing speech immediately [4].

Having analyzed the samples of adapted preschool educational programs for children with severe speech disorders edited by L.V. Lopatina, N.V. Nishcheva, as well as a comprehensive speech therapy program to address the general speech underdevelopment in children edited by T.B. Filicheva and G.V. Chirkina that is widely used in speech therapy in preschool educational institutions, we revealed the need to develop dialogue speech in children of senior preschool age with general speech underdevelopment.

In their educational program, T.B. Filicheva and G.V. Chirkina recommend start developing dialogic speech from the first stage of speech therapy for children with different speech skills and suffering from general speech underdevelopment. Children having basic speech skills only do not have the ability to speak. In this regard, they practice to learn the conceptual dialogue component. Thus, basing on the story picture, the teacher sets a question, while the child gives an answer by using gestures. Children with medium speech skills undergoing speech therapy had developed basic skills required for dialogue construction during the first stage of speech therapy. At the second stage of speech therapy, dialogue-based interaction skills are improved: adequate answers to questions, literate question formation, readdressing the question to the interlocutor. Considering children of preschool age with general speech underdevelopment who have reached the third level of speech development, speech therapy is aimed at developing an adequate perception of the speech utterance, as well as the ability to hold a preparatory dialogue [5].

In her adapted principal educational program for children with severe speech disabilities (general speech underdevelopment), which compiles to the Federal Educational Standards for preschool education, L.V. Lopatina recommends applying to psycholinguistics as the base for speech therapy, since speech is a multicomponent function that includes semantics, syntax, lexicology, grammar, phonetics and phonematics. These components develop due to intensive and extensive impacting, as well as through building a linguistic intuition.

The third stage of speech therapy corresponding to the senior preschool age assumes developing coherent speech within the speech development educational domain. This is the case when it is important to activate speech in children with general speech underdevelopment, support their initiative to conduct a dialogue with peers. Children with general speech underdevelopment should be motivated by being engaged into a certain speech situation. The motivation tool can involve a didactic game with a plot in which children with a general speech underdevelopment personate some characters and conduct a dialogue to continue the game.

The program recommends forming an impact aimed at creating a dialogue through the communicative game environment simulating it so that it would motivate children to get engaged into communication with peers and adults. First, specialists have to teach preschool children with general speech underdevelopment how to use communicative game environment together in order to create conditions for dialogue communication [3].

In her adapted principal preschool educational program for children at the age of 3 to 7 with severe speech disorders (general speech underdevelopment), N.V. Nishcheva proposes speech therapy based on humanity and considering personal characteristics of children with general speech underdevelopment, which addresses not only corrective tasks, but also contributes to developing personal qualities in children of preschool age with general speech underdevelopment, and also has a positive impact on developing the cognitive sphere and mental functions in general.

The program content is notable for its persistent influence of the speech skills on building relationships and communication between a child having general speech underdevelopment and the society around. Dialogue speech should be considered as the fundamental of productive communication. As a result, one of the key tasks of the program is to develop dialogic speech in children with general speech underdevelopment. It also defines the most effective methods for implementing educational and corrective tasks. Correctional and educational work to develop dialogic speech in children of senior preschool age with general speech underdevelopment is based on teaching children to briefly and quickly answer the questions, as well as comprehensively listen to speaker's remarks. For these purposes, the speech therapy applies to game competitions, theatricalization, games aimed at developing ingenuity, active games, issue-related and free drawing, improvised conversations, literary quizzes, etc.

Speech therapy for preschool children with general speech underdevelopment aims at developing dialogic speech through motivating to describe, express their opinion and attitudes to what children see. In addition, children with general speech underdevelopment learn how to build a literate dialogue with other people by asking adequate questions, as well as briefly and concisely answer the questions. With that said, these problems are to be addressed both informally, and in learning activity directly [2].

Having analyzed the adapted principal preschool educational programs for children with severe speech disabilities, it should be noted that game activity and gaming in general is the most effective tool to develop dialogic speech. Learning through game is the leading activity for children of preschool age, so it should be comprehensively studied.

Summarizing all the above, it can be concluded that it is the senior preschool age that is the most sensitive period for dialogic speech development. That is why this communication form should be based on when developing speech interaction in classes, through both daily routines, and gaming activities.

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